

Further elution of the column with benzene afforded β -sitosterol, m.p. 135-36°, acetate m.p. 127-28°, identical (m.m.p. and co-tlc) with authentic sample.

Benzene extract of the defatted plant on usual chromatographic resolution over silica gel furnished triacontanol and β -sitosterol, while chloroform extract on chromatographic resolution yielded only triacontanol.

P. parviflora: The air dried powdered whole plant of *P. parviflora* was extracted successively with petroleum ether (60-80°), benzene and chloroform. The concentrated petroleum ether (60-80°) extract was chromatographed over Brockmann alumina. Elution of the column with petroleum ether (60-80°) benzene (1:1) mixture gave a solid crystallisable from methanol in shining white flakes, m.p. 135-36°. It responded positive in Leibermann-Burchardt test and was characterised as β -sitosterol by m.m.p. and co-ir with authentic sample. Further elution of the column with the same solvent yielded another sterol crystallised from chloroform-methanol (1:1) mixture, m.p. 145-46°; acetate m.p. 144°, identified as γ -sitosterol from m.m.p. co-tlc and co-ir with authentic specimen. The concentrated benzene and chloroform extract of the plant on chromatography over alumina yielded only β -sitosterol.

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Chemical Investigation of *Alysicarpus longifolius* Leaves

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*ALYSICARPUS longifolius*¹ Wright and Arn (Leguminosae), an annual herb commonly grows throughout the tropical region. The plant is reputed

for its medicinal values² and potential use as a forage. Literature revealed that no work, has been reported on the chemistry of this plant. Isolation and identification of myricyl alcohol, β -sitosterol, β -sitosterol acetate, rutin, pinitol along with an aliphatic ester and a flavonol are reported here. The latter two are being investigated further. The identity of the compounds was established on the basis of m.m.p. co-tlc, uv, ir, mass and comparison with authentic samples.

Experimental

The leaves were collected locally during July and August and contained crude protein 20.7, calcium 2.24 and phosphorus 0.29%. Powdered air-dried leaves (1 kg) were exhaustively extracted with ethanol (95%) under reflux. The alcoholic extract on concentration and cooling deposited a yellow crystalline compound (B). The remaining extract was successively fractionated into petroleum ether, benzene, ethyl-acetate and butanol fractions.

Petroleum ether fraction: It was chromatographed on silica gel column. Elution with different solvents and their mixtures yielded the following compounds. Compound A, (Petroleum ether-benzene 8:2). On crystallisation from acetone a white crystalline product m.p. 74°, MS (m/e M⁺ 732) was obtained showing strong ir absorption at 1740 and 1175 cm⁻¹ suggestive of an aliphatic ester. Myricyl alcohol³; m.p. and mm.p. with an authentic sample, 86-87°, acetate, m.p. 70-71°; β -sitosterol^{3,4}-m.p. 136-137°, (α)_D - 33°; acetate, m.p. 129°; β -sitosterol acetate, m.p. 129°.

Ethyl acetate fraction: Rutin m.p. 186-187°, identical (m.p. and ir) with an authentic sample.

Butanol fraction: Pinitol m.p. 186°, identical (ms and ir) with an authentic specimen, penta-acetate, m.p. 98°.

Compound B, was obtained from alcohol as yellow crystals m.p. 197°, gave positive Shinoda Test⁴⁻⁵ (Mg+HCl) for flavonol, uv

λ (MeOH)_{max} 272, 335, nm : λ (MeOH+AlCl₃)_{max} 279, 352, nm :

λ (MeOH+AlCl₃+HCl)_{max} 291, 352 nm : λ (MeOH+NaOMe)_{max} 277,

362 nm. There was no shift on addition of sodium acetate. The ir spectrum exhibited characteristic peaks at ν _{max}^{KBr} 3400, 2920, 1645, 1590, 1550, 1485 and 1445 ;

acetate (acetic anhydride+pyridine) crystallized from methanol as colourless silky needles m.p. 179°.

IR ν _{max}^{KBr} 1740 cm⁻¹, ms (m/e M⁺ 656).

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Chemical Investigation of Pod Husk of *Cassia auriculata* Linn

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CASSIA auriculata Linn. is a small perennial shrub growing wild in Rajasthan and Central India and is well known for its medicinal and economic values¹. It has been studied for its flavonoids²⁻⁴, tannins⁵, anthraquinones⁶ and certain proteolytic enzymes^{7,8}. The present paper deals with the isolation and identification of chrysophanol, emodin and rubiadin from pod husk of the plant. Though chrysophanol and emodin have been reported from several *Cassia* species, rubiadin has not so far been reported from any.

The chloroform extract of powdered pod husk, after removing petroleum ether fraction, was chromatographed over silica-gel column using benzene and chloroform in varying proportions as eluent. It yielded four compounds one of which was a white crystalline compound identified as β -sitosterol, already reported from this plant. The three other compounds had melting points 196°, 256° and 301°.

The yellow coloured compound m.p. 196°, $C_{15}H_{10}O_4$ (M^+254) gave orange-red colour with methanolic magnesium acetate⁹ and red colour with sodium dithionate in alkaline solution¹⁰. Ultraviolet and infrared spectra suggested it to be a 1, 8-dihydroxy anthraquinone (1625 cm^{-1} for chelated carbonyl and 1670 cm^{-1} for non-chelated carbonyl)¹¹. The compound was identified as chrysophanol (1, 8-dihydroxy-3 methyl anthraquinone) by m.m.p. and co-tlc of acetyl and methyl derivatives with authentic samples.

The second orange coloured compound m.p. 256°, $C_{15}H_{10}O_5$ (M^+270) gave pink colour with methanolic magnesium acetate⁹ and red colour with sodium dithionate in alkaline solution¹⁰.

Ultraviolet and infrared spectra suggested it to be a dihydroxy anthraquinone with one free OH group at position 2, 3, 6 or 7 (3390 cm^{-1} free -OH; 1670 cm^{-1} non-chelated C=O; 1625 cm^{-1} chelated C=O)¹¹. The compound was identified as emodin (1,6,8-trihydroxy-3-methyl anthraquinone) by m.m.p., co-tlc and ir.

The third yellow coloured compound, m.p. 310° $C_{15}H_{10}O_4$ (M^+254) gave positive tests with methanolic magnesium acetate⁹. Ultraviolet and infrared spectra suggested it to be a 1, 3-dihydroxy anthraquinone (3420 cm^{-1} , free -OH; 1650 cm^{-1} non-chelated carbonyl, and 1625 cm^{-1} chelated carbonyl group)¹¹. It was identified as rubiadin by m.m.p., co-tlc and ir of its acetyl and methyl derivatives with those of an authentic specimen. Rubiadin is thus reported for the first time in *Cassia* species.

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A Note on the Antibacterial Action of Some 2-Anilinoacetyl-5-Nitrofurans

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It has been shown by Sherman¹ that compounds in which the nitrofur ring is directly attached to a heterocyclic ring exhibit antibacterial activity. Since then a number of nitrofuryl heterocycles have

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